

ENSURING THE STABILITY AND LIQUIDITY OF THE BANK-CREDIT SYSTEM

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***Abstract** The banking system is one of the main links of the financial market, the development of which, on the one hand, is an impetus for the development of the country's financial sector, and on the other hand, as a result of financing the real sector, leads to the development of the functioning of production facilities, the development of the economy.*

***Keywords:** banking, innovation, credit, small business, income, financial.*

Today, the technical and technological development of banks is of particular importance in the development of the banking system. In this process, one of the main tasks facing the system is to firmly establish the provision of modern innovative services, and to attract public deposits to it by guaranteeing the bank's obligations.

In the conditions of modernization and liberalization of the economy, one of the important tasks is to improve the functions of the financial market, to develop an alternative operation strategy of the banking system, which is its main participant. One of the main tasks of commercial banks is to provide customers with innovative financial services and ensure their popularity. In order to ensure the effective implementation of this task, it is important to increase the attractiveness of the banking system, that is, to gain the customers' trust, convenience and, most importantly, the trust of their customers. Chain-like sequence should operate in a continuous manner in all links of the economy, including in the banking system.

Disruption of the sequence in the banking system leads to non-arrival of the expected income, which leads to a decrease in stability and liquidity levels. If we analyze the section of transactions carried out in our banks today, in the composition of asset operations, only credit and leasing operations have increased by 15.02%, which is certainly a positive situation, but only a decrease in the structure of other income-generating asset operations is the answer to many such questions. finding, analyzing them and offering an effective solution ensures the bank's income. For this, it is necessary to study to what extent bank customers have the opportunity to use these types of services. At the same time, if we pay attention to the theoretical approaches of our country's economists regarding the financial services of commercial banks, the banking service is a view of banking activity that helps the optimal execution of banking operations provided to clients. [1] A. N. Azriliyan, one of the foreign economists, defines "Financial services as activities related to attracting and using funds of individuals and legal entities".[3] Another economist Ye.B.Shirinskaya describes that "banks' consulting services are included in off-balance sheet practices, because their provision does not lead to an increase in assets and liabilities, and the payment consists of commissions." .[3] The American scientist P. S. Rose included such types of banking activities as management of money reserves, consumer credit, cash flow management, leasing, and sale of pension plans. [2] observed: funds for trading operations, that is, securities and investments, which indicates that our banks are limited to lending and do not have a diversification policy. This situation can also be seen in passive operations. Demand deposits account for more than 60 percent, time deposits for more than 20 percent, and savings deposits for more than 10 percent. This situation indicates that there is no balance in deposits in our banks today, which in itself is formed on the basis of the financial resources of legal entities and operates on the basis of high risk.

Taking into account the dependence of one factor on another factor, in solving these problems, in implementing fundamental changes in the banking system, the main task is to increase the weight of financial services, manage them in an innovative way, improve the banking infrastructure, and eliminate negative factors affecting income. elimination is required. Because we can see that banks carry out more than 300 operations in foreign practice. Commercial banks in our country are limited to lending and accepting deposits. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to increase the types of financial services and to form the basis for expanding the bank's sources of income. In particular, we can see the rating of banks in Uzbekistan in Table 1:

Table 1. Bank activity rating in Uzbekistan ¹

No	Name of the bank	Overall rating	Rating change	On financial	Ranking by	On capital adequacy	Asset quality rating	On management	Earning potential	Liquidity rating
1.	Capital Bank	1	0	1	1	13	1	2	12	3
2.	Hamkor bank	2	1	7	4	9	3	6	2	8
3.	Trust bank	3	-1	6	9	7	6	7	1	2
4.	Asia Alliance Bank	4	0	1	10	17	7	10	11	6
5.	Invest Finance Bank	5	1	1	12	14	2	10	11	6

In the implementation of these tasks, it is necessary to study the level of popularity of the types of financial services offered in banks. Because the provided service, i.e. the bank product, has its customer, does it meet the requirements, does the customer have the knowledge of using this type of service, what are the

¹ <https://www.spot.uz/oz/2023/09/27/bank-index/>

indicators of adoption, and in the analysis of the theoretical views of the above economists, financial services meet the benefits and needs of customers is defined as a service aimed at satisfying and, at the same time, increasing the bank's profit. Summarizing these definitions, we can say that financial services are a mechanism for innovative implementation of customer benefits and bank income. This is the most recent data for top banks as of January 30 th, 2023. These bank rankings are compiled from balance sheet information included in LexisNexis® Bankers Almanac® Counterparty KYC, the look-up tool that enables Know Your Customer (KYC) analysts in your organization to identify counterparties from almost 200,000 financial institutions.

Table 2. Rating of banks in the world²

Current Rank	Previous Rank	Bank	Assets US\$ (Millions)	+ or - (local currency)	Capital US\$ (Millions)	Balance Sheet Date
1	1	Industrial & Commercial Bank of China Limited	5,518,390.00	+8.02%	111,515.00	31.12.2021
2	2	China Construction Bank Corporation	4,746,849.00	+10.14%	39,227.00	31.12.2021
3	3	Agricultural Bank of China Limited	4,560,950.00	+9.43%	67,448.00	31.12.2021
4	4	Bank of China Limited	4,192,746.00	+12.15%	46,189.00	31.12.2021
5	6	JPMorgan Chase Bank National Association	3,306,982.00	+9.31%	2,028.00	31.12.2021
6	5	BNP Paribas SA	2,982,191.00	-2.41%	29,825.00	31.12.2021
7	7	China Development Bank	2,693,650.00	+2.80%	66,094.00	31.12.2021
8	10	Bank of America National Association	2,519,525.00	+11.54%	3,020.00	31.12.2021
9	9	MUFG Bank Ltd.	2,359,275.00	+0.00%	15,536.00	31.03.2021
10	8	Crédit Agricole SA	2,347,717.00	-2.51%	9,905.00	31.12.2021

Based on this, it became clear that increasing the popularity of financial services is a practical help for the development of our country's economy. As we have mentioned above, the hypothesis of the integral dependence of one factor on another factor was formed. We will have the opportunity to manage asset and liability operations of commercial banks based on the expansion of the scope of financial services, which will have a positive effect on the increase in the income

² <https://risk.lexisnexis.com/insights-resources/article/bank-rankings-top-banks-in-the-world>

of banks, the level of liquidity and stability. We will be able to achieve these results based on ensuring the popularity of financial services. Bringing it up to the level of economically developed countries, especially in rural areas: studying the real requirements of the population, developing the service sector in accordance with available resources and capabilities, providing technologies that meet today's requirements, increasing customer awareness, raising the level of employees and mass media will be achieved on the basis of establishing an integrated activity with commercial banks.

Summary

In our opinion, based on the analysis of the scientific works of foreign scientists, we can conclude that their proposals and experiences will allow increasing the popularity of financial services in the banking system of our country.

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